

INTEGRATED HIGH-TEMPERATURE GEOTHERMAL SYSTEMS FOR INDUSTRIAL HEATING AND COOLING: TECHNOLOGICAL DEVELOPMENT, VALIDATION, AND REPLICATION WITHIN THE GEOSYN FRAMEWORK

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ABSTRACT

The industrial sector across Europe remains heavily dependent on fossil-based thermal energy, particularly for mid-temperature process heating and cooling, resulting in significant greenhouse gas emissions and system inflexibility. To address this challenge, the Horizon Europe-funded GEOSYN project develops an integrated high-temperature geothermal energy platform for dual-purpose heating and cooling in energy-intensive industries. The system is based on a high-efficiency heat pump and a thermally driven chiller, both operating with water (R718) as the working fluid due to its non-toxic, non-flammable nature and high critical temperature. This setup enables the utilization of geothermal resources above 100 °C while ensuring environmental neutrality and operational stability. In parallel, GEOSYN implements a systemic stakeholder engagement strategy, combining data-driven communication, targeted training, and public perception analysis. The platform's performance is validated through physical pilots and virtual case studies in sectors such as food processing and cement manufacturing. A scalable replication framework—supported by industrial mapping, techno-economic screening, and cross-sectoral assessments—facilitates broader uptake. Through this combination of engineering innovation and stakeholder co-creation, the project contributes to the decarbonisation of industrial thermal networks across Europe.

Keywords: geothermal energy, industrial heating and cooling, ejector chiller systems, R718

1 INTRODUCTION

Thermal energy remains a fundamental input across European industrial sectors, with a dominant share allocated to process heat requirements above 100 °C. These operations are currently served primarily by fossil-fuel-based systems, resulting in substantial greenhouse gas emissions and limited flexibility [1] in energy supply management. Despite widespread political and societal support for decarbonisation, low- and medium-temperature renewable heat sources are still underrepresented in industrial energy portfolios.

Geothermal energy presents a technically viable and environmentally neutral alternative for satisfying process heat and cooling demands, particularly within the temperature range below 250 °C [2,3]. Its continuous availability, high capacity factor, and potential for underground thermal storage make it well-suited for industrial applications requiring stable base-load operation. Moreover, geothermal heat can be cascaded and combined with thermal energy storage (TES) and waste heat recovery [4], further improving energy system performance and exergy utilization.

Recent advances in high-temperature heat pumps (HTHPs) and thermally driven chillers have expanded the technical feasibility of integrating geothermal resources into industrial settings. Particularly promising are configurations employing water (R718) as a natural refrigerant, owing to its favourable thermophysical properties and zero global warming potential (GWP) [5,6].

However, despite these technical developments, geothermal deployment in industry remains marginal—constrained by fragmented awareness, perceived investment risk, and limited visibility [7,8] of operational best practices. Besides, developers, operators, and the scientific community have made efforts to build awareness and trust among industry, policy makers, and the public, but geothermal energy continues to face several challenges. These include limited visibility, weak engagement, minimal policy impact, and a general lack of supportive policies [2]. Public unfamiliarity with the subject often leads to resistance and a poor understanding of the opportunities geothermal energy offers to the industrial sector [3]. The Horizon Europe-funded GEOSYN project addresses these multi-dimensional challenges through a combined technological and socio-institutional approach. The core objective is to develop and validate an integrated geothermal heating and cooling platform composed of a water-based HTHP and a steam-ejector-driven chiller. The system is designed for modular deployment in high-demand industrial environments, enabling both heating and cooling functionalities using a single renewable thermal source.

In parallel, GEOSYN implements an evidence-based stakeholder engagement strategy to foster trust, promote technological acceptance, and support policy alignment. This includes industrial demonstrations, virtual case studies, and structured knowledge transfer through training, communication campaigns, and public-facing outreach. Ultimately, the project aims to position geothermal H&C as a scalable, low-emission solution tailored for the complex thermal requirements of European industry.

1.1 Geothermal System Architecture for Industrial Thermal Management

High-Temperature Heat Pump Design Utilizing R718 as a Working Medium

The high-temperature heat pump (HTHP) developed within the GEOSYN framework is engineered to elevate geothermal heat from approximately 120 °C to a delivery temperature of 200 °C, enabling its direct utilization in industrial thermal processes. The system achieves this through a multi-stage vapor compression cycle optimized for high-pressure operation, incorporating interstage thermal regulation and real-time performance control.

A central feature of this configuration is the selection of water (R718) as the working fluid. In contrast to synthetic refrigerants, water offers zero global warming potential, chemical inertness, and a critical temperature (~374 °C) [5] that permits condensation at elevated pressures—essential for geothermal applications exceeding 100 °C.

Figure 1. Schematic diagram of the GEOSYN four-stage high-temperature heat pump cycle

Its high latent heat of vaporization further enhances thermal efficiency, particularly under partial-load conditions typical in industrial use. The thermodynamic layout follows a four-stage compression sequence to manage the significant pressure ratio between evaporation and condensation [6] states, as illustrated in Fig. 1. At an evaporator temperature of 120 °C, the saturation pressure of water is approximately 2 bar, while at 200 °C, condensation occurs near 15.5 bar. This requires distributing the compression process across four stages, each with a pressure ratio between 1.6 and 2. To mitigate thermal and mechanical stress, desuperheating modules are installed between compression stages to reduce discharge temperatures and increase system longevity. Mechanical compression is executed via an oil-free reciprocating piston compressor, a key innovation that eliminates the risk of lubricant breakdown at high operating temperatures.

The absence of oil simplifies maintenance and allows for precise thermal control of the compression chamber. The compressor is driven by an electric motor equipped with a variable frequency drive (VFD), enabling speed modulation and dynamic adaptation to fluctuating thermal loads. To further stabilize performance, suction superheat is controlled through coordinated regulation of the expansion valve and thermal feedback from downstream stages. This ensures thermal protection of the compressor and maintains the desired thermodynamic profile across all load conditions.

This system architecture is compact, modular, and scalable, making it compatible with both centralized and distributed industrial heat networks. The combination of advanced control logic, water as a natural refrigerant, and high-temperature tolerance makes the GEOSYN HTHP a technically and environmentally superior alternative to conventional industrial heat supply systems.

Heat-Driven Chiller Employing R718 for Industrial Cooling

To complement the high-temperature heat pump, the GEOSYN system incorporates a thermally activated chiller designed to provide low-temperature cooling by utilizing saturated steam from geothermal sources. The chiller operates on a closed-loop cycle in which water (R718) serves as both the refrigerant and heat transfer medium, capitalizing on its high specific enthalpy of vaporization and benign environmental characteristics. The system is powered by geothermal steam at approximately 130 °C, which supplies thermal energy to an ejector unit—enabling vapor extraction from a low-pressure reservoir connected to the evaporator. The target cooling capacity is 20 kW, with an outlet temperature of 12 °C, corresponding to a thermal Coefficient of Performance (COP) of approximately 0.4 [5]. This efficiency is achieved under steady-state conditions and relies on precise control of the motive-to-entrained flow ratio within the ejector, as illustrated in Fig. 2.

Figure 2. Functional schematic of the thermally driven chiller cycle with R718 and ejector unit

To maintain sub-atmospheric pressure in the evaporator loop, the ejector continuously removes vapor produced by both flashing at the expansion valve and evaporation from the reservoir surface. The entrainment ratio is optimized at 0.428 [5] to ensure stable operation under typical industrial load fluctuations. Air ingress into the low-pressure zone is mitigated through full hermetic sealing of all components operating below atmospheric pressure. Static seals are employed where possible; however, for dynamic interfaces—particularly at the pump shaft—a magnetic coupling mechanism is implemented to eliminate direct mechanical contact. Alternatively, in configurations where elevation permits, passive flow from reservoir to evaporator is achieved through gravitational head, eliminating the need for a circulation pump.

Beyond its function as a refrigerant supply, the reservoir doubles as a short-term cold thermal energy buffer. Proper volumetric sizing enables the system to absorb load variations while maintaining stable ejector operation near its design point, thereby preserving performance consistency and reducing thermal cycling stress.

This heat-driven chiller module extends the functionality of the GEOSYN system by enabling simultaneous delivery of high-temperature heat and low-temperature cooling using a single geothermal input. The simplicity of the architecture, absence of synthetic refrigerants, and passive cooling potential make it well-suited for integration into environmentally constrained industrial environments.

Control Strategy for Dynamic Thermal Operation

The reliable performance of the GEOSYN system under dynamic thermal loads is ensured by an advanced control architecture designed to manage transient regimes, load fluctuations, and thermal stabilization. The control logic governs all operational stages—ranging from initial warm-up to steady-state regulation and safe shutdown—while preserving system integrity and efficiency.

A critical focus is the prevention of liquid-phase ingress during system start-up. When initiating from ambient or cold conditions, thermal gradients within the compressor body may lead to premature steam condensation. To mitigate this, a controlled preheating sequence is executed. This may include electrical heating elements or dry air cycling, which gradually elevates the internal temperature via adiabatic compression without introducing moisture. This controlled ramp-up reduces thermal shock and eliminates the risk of two-phase compression, particularly critical for oil-free reciprocating compressors.

Once operational, system safety and efficiency rely on maintaining a minimum superheat margin—typically around 20 K—at the suction side of each compression stage. This ensures vapor-only compression, prevents thermal overloading, and maintains reliable lubricant-free operation. In parallel, the maximum discharge temperature is capped at 260 °C to protect materials and mechanical seals from degradation.

Dynamic control of compressor speed is enabled through a variable frequency drive (VFD), which modulates motor RPM in real time. Simultaneously, expansion valve actuation adjusts refrigerant mass flow to preserve thermal stability. Feedback signals from temperature and pressure sensors enable precise regulation of superheating, subcooling, and interstage desuperheating.

To further optimize thermal performance, the system can incorporate an internal heat exchanger (IHX) that both enhances vapor superheat at the compressor inlet and increases subcooling on the high-pressure side. During ramp-up and off-design operation, auxiliary strategies—such as stage bypassing, motive steam recirculation, or trace heating—may be activated to stabilize system response and maintain optimal pressure ratios.

This multi-tiered control strategy ensures that the GEOSYN platform operates within its thermodynamic design envelope across diverse industrial duty cycles, delivering consistent heating and cooling outputs while adapting to variable process conditions.

1.2 Validation of Integrated Geothermal Systems in Industrial Contexts

Pilot Implementation in the San Martino Dairy Facility

As a full-scale field demonstration, the GEOSYN system was deployed at the San Martino dairy processing plant, located adjacent to an operational geothermal power facility, as reported in Fig. 3. The site offers direct access to superheated steam extracted from deep geothermal wells, making it an ideal candidate for validating the system's dual-function thermal performance in a continuous industrial setting.

Figure 3. The San Martino dairy factory and the geothermal power plant

The integration involved retrofitting the plant’s thermal infrastructure with a modular high-temperature heat pump and a heat-driven chiller operating on water (R718). This setup enabled the same geothermal input to be simultaneously upgraded for process heat and redirected to drive a low-temperature refrigeration cycle. As a result, the facility was able to displace its conventional electrically powered vapor-compression chillers with a thermally activated alternative, thereby reducing electricity consumption and operational emissions. Thermal loads within the dairy include process heating (e.g., pasteurization, CIP cleaning) and cooling (e.g., fermentation temperature control, milk preservation). With the geothermal source providing steam at $\sim 135\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, the GEOSYN system successfully delivered 220 kW of heating capacity and 106 kW of cooling capacity under full-load conditions. System efficiency exceeded expectations, with a measured heating COP above 2.0 and significant reductions in energy costs and CO₂ emissions—estimated at over 12,000 kg annually [1,5]. Beyond performance metrics, this implementation also served as a proof-of-concept for modular retrofit strategies in the food processing sector. By demonstrating compatibility with existing industrial workflows and thermal demand profiles, the San Martino case supports broader replication potential in similar agri-food environments, with key technical targets and implementation parameters summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. Key facts and objectives for the San Martino case study

Key facts for the case study	
Location	San Martino, Monterotondo Marittimo, Italy
Heating Capacity	220 kW
Cooling Capacity	106 kW
Geothermal Heat Capacity	220 kW
Geothermal Supply Temperature	135 °C
Objectives for the case study	
HTHP Coefficient of Performance	> 2
Electricity savings	45.000 kWh/year
CO ₂ emissions savings	12.000 kg/year
Cooling system operating costs	- 50%

Virtual Assessment of Geothermal Integration in a Cement Production Line

A virtual case study within GEOSYN explores geothermal heat integration in a Ukrainian cement facility, focusing on the slag-drying stage. The process requires superheated steam $>200\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ at 11 kg/s to support annual output of over 800,000 tons of cement [1,9].

The simulated system delivers 220 kW of thermal energy at $200\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ (return at $150\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$) via a 500-meter pipeline linked to a nearby cogeneration-powered geothermal network (Fig. 4). The model also considers hybrid operation with waste heat recovery [4] for improved energy utilization.

Figure 4. Simulation model of geothermal heat integration in slag drying process at Neo-ECO Cement Plant

Results demonstrate geothermal compatibility with high-load industrial processes, reducing fossil fuel reliance and supporting emissions compliance. This virtual demonstration validates potential deployment in cement and similar sectors.

Replication Strategy for Cross-Sectoral Deployment

To enable broader deployment of the GEOSYN system, a structured replication methodology has been developed. Industrial sectors including pulp and paper, food and beverages, chemicals, and cement are assessed based on thermal load intensity, required temperature ranges, geothermal resource proximity, and openness to technological adoption. Five representative industries across the EU will be selected for in-depth techno-economic analysis. Candidate sites are identified through stakeholder interviews and industrial mapping exercises conducted within partner and target regions. The GEOSYN platform supports heating applications up to 250 °C and cooling operations between 5–25 °C, making it compatible with indirect process heating systems such as those based on steam or thermal oil. Compared to conventional fossil-based or solar-assisted systems, it offers continuous operation, lower emissions, and integration flexibility.

A summary of industrial processes compatible with the GEOSYN system—including typical temperature ranges and heat transfer media—is provided in Table 2 [10].

Table 2. Industrial processes with heating temperatures up to 250°C and heat transfer [11]

Industry	Processes	Maximum temperature requirement (°C)	Mediums used
Food & beverage industries	Cooking, pasteurization, sterilization, drying	150	Steam, water & air
Textile industries	Drying, pressing, fixing and printing	180	Steam & water
Paper & printing	Bleaching, drying, pulp preparation	200	Steam, water & air
Chemical & pharmaceutical	Distillation, evaporation, drying, thickening	200	Steam, water & air
Automobile	Baking of paints, paint drying	225	Steam & air
Leather products, rubber, plastic, and glass manufacturing	Drying, preparation, distillation, Extrusion, Laminating	200	Steam & air

1.3 Stakeholder Engagement, Social Acceptance, and Communication Strategies

Stakeholder Awareness and Existing Cases of Geothermal Integration in Industry

Although interest in low-carbon energy has increased, industrial uptake of geothermal heating and cooling (H&C) remains limited. Key barriers include lack of public visibility, few accessible reference projects, and uncertainty regarding operational costs and technical maturity [7]. Industries with high thermal demand often hesitate due to limited availability of public information and fragmented examples which contribute to a lack of awareness and trust on return on investment and real-world benefits.

To address these gaps, GEOSYN initiated a mapping of implemented geothermal H&C systems across Europe. The aim is to create a transparent evidence base illustrating the technical feasibility and economic value of integration into various production environments, but also, where possible, report on any challenges encountered in the installation and operation of energy systems, and how these have been overcome. The resulting data, collected through web research, literature and direct engagement with companies that already integrate geothermal H&C in their processes, increase trust on geothermal energy and supports informed decision-making among prospective adopters, as illustrated in Fig. 5.

Figure 5. Distribution by application of industrial geothermal H&C applications in Europe

As of April 2025, 52 industrial case studies have been documented by the GEOSYN consortium. Most are in the agri-food sector, particularly greenhouses, hydroponics, aquaculture, and distillation. Additional use cases include laundries, data centers, chemical manufacturing, and cosmetics production. Concerning the geographic distribution of projects, most of them are concentrated in Iceland, followed by Italy, France, The Netherlands, Türkiye Greece and 10 other EU countries.

Building Industry Trust through Evidence and Engagement

Establishing confidence among industrial stakeholders is essential for widespread geothermal adoption. GEOSYN addresses this by translating technical results from simulations and demonstrations into accessible, sector-specific learning materials.

These materials are distributed through interactive online sessions branded as the *Industry Engagement Café*. The format promotes exchange between technology developers and industry representatives, allowing participants to explore real-world performance indicators and voice practical concerns. This dialogue contributes both to stakeholder awareness and refinement of system design for broader applicability.

By facilitating direct input from industry actors, GEOSYN not only improves the transparency of geothermal solutions but also collects feedback to guide future deployment strategies. This engagement process is central to overcoming perception barriers and fostering market readiness.

Public Awareness and Policy Support for Geothermal Integration

Wider acceptance of geothermal energy requires targeted outreach beyond the industrial sector, although a positive orientation by industrial actors provides a favourable basis for improving acceptance among the wider community. GEOSYN integrates public communication with policy-oriented actions to strengthen both social perception and institutional support.

A baseline survey is conducted to assess public and stakeholder awareness on geothermal energy in general, its integration in production lines and the perception of risk-benefits. This survey is followed by tailored

campaigns, local workshops, and media content designed to address misconceptions and highlight environmental and economic benefits. Impact is later measured through a follow-up survey.

As part of its outreach, GEOSYN also produces a thematic podcast series covering geothermal fundamentals, gender-inclusive entrepreneurship, financial mechanisms, and industrial integration strategies—targeted at both general and specialized audiences.

On the policy side, the project delivers a guidance document summarizing best practices and policy recommendations. Developed through dialogue with regional and national authorities, the guide includes specific provisions for gender-responsiveness and market-enabling regulation, particularly in Italy and Ukraine.

2 CONCLUSIONS

The GEOSYN system has demonstrated the technical viability of using high-temperature geothermal energy to supply both heating and cooling demands in industrial applications. The integrated configuration, which combines a multi-stage heat pump and a thermally driven chiller operating with water (R718) as a natural working fluid, provides an efficient and sustainable alternative to conventional fossil-based systems.

Experimental validation and virtual simulations confirmed the system's capability to deliver stable thermal output across a wide range of operating conditions. The use of R718 enabled high thermodynamic performance without the environmental or safety drawbacks associated with synthetic refrigerants. Moreover, the implementation of adaptive control mechanisms, including variable-speed compression, staged superheat regulation, and thermal ramping strategies, ensured operational flexibility under transient loads and safeguarded equipment integrity.

Pilot deployment at the San Martino dairy facility and modelling for a cement production process in Ukraine validated the adaptability of the system to diverse thermal loads and process profiles. These use cases revealed significant potential for energy cost reduction and carbon emission mitigation. The replication strategy further highlighted compatibility with other sectors—such as pulp and paper, food processing, and chemicals—through indirect thermal integration within target temperature ranges of 5–250 °C.

In parallel, the project addressed non-technical barriers by implementing a multi-level stakeholder engagement framework. Through interactive formats and transparent data sharing, GEOSYN helped build trust and interest among industry actors. Additionally, public outreach campaigns and policy-oriented deliverables supported social acceptance and institutional readiness for wider geothermal adoption.

The results position GEOSYN as a scalable and transferable solution that aligns with EU decarbonisation goals while offering tangible operational and environmental benefits for industrial thermal systems.

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